

The Role of Time Reversal and Possible Number of Reactions on Equilibrium Part 3

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 16, 2025

In Parts 1 and 2, we tried to argue that an unambiguous statistical picture of Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) gases arises from reaction balance. In particular, even though reaction balance only applies to large N cases (in order to make an e_1, e_2 reaction independent from the rest of the system), a clear conserved statistical quantity representing the number of possible successful reactions exists in all three cases, even in the large N limit. The expression for the total number of possible successful reactions is not an approximation, unlike the $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ Stirling's approximation case.

In Parts 1 and 2, we tried to link this statistical reaction balance approach to an entropy function mathematically. Here, we argue taking \ln of the reaction balance case and using the notion of Sum over i $dG(p(e_i)) = A \text{ Sum over } i e_i dp(e_i) + B \text{ Sum over } i dp(e_i) = 0$, makes use of $\ln(\text{probability}(j))$ where probability j is any product type probability present in a product reaction balance equation. This means that multiplying $\ln(\text{probability}(j))$ by probability(j) immediately gives a Stirling's approximation form: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ because the derivative of this expression must either contribute to an $e_i dp(e_i)$ term or a $dp(e_i)$ one. As a result, the exact statistical conserved number of possible reactions maps to an approximate Stirling's form which may be interpreted as the $\ln(n(j)!) / n(j)!$ where $n(j)!$ is the number of ways of permuting $n(j)$ identical particles. Given this physical interpretation, one may consider $\text{Sum over } i dG(p(e_i)) = 0$ as representing $N!$ (or a similar N function) divided by the number of permutations of identical particles, i.e. a unique set of ordering which respects identical particles. This leads to the notion of entropy as \ln (number of orderings), however, these orderings are not states in the FD or BE case, but are linked to successful reactions. Furthermore, given the non-exactness of Stirling's approximation, this seems to be a somewhat approximate approach which is created mathematically.

Reaction Balance

A key idea we wish to stress is that even though reaction balance only applies for $N \rightarrow \infty$, so that one may isolate an $e_1, e_2 \rightarrow e_k, e_l$ reaction for $e_1 + e_2 = e_k + e_l$, each side of the balance equation exactly represents the number of possible reactions which may occur. No approximation appears in this conserved statistical quantity.

MB case: $N! p(e_1) p(e_2) = N! p(e_k) p(e_l)$ with $e_1 + e_2 = e_k + e_l$ ((1a))

FD case: $N! p(e_1) (1-p(e_k)) p(e_2) (1-p(e_l)) = N! p(e_k) (1-p(e_1)) p(e_l) (1-p(e_2))$ ((1b))

BE case: $N! p(e_1) (1+p(e_k)) p(e_2) (1+p(e_l)) = N! p(e_k) (1+p(e_1)) p(e_l) (1+p(e_2))$ ((1c))

In the FD case, it is not enough to have an e_1 present, its neighbour at the reaction point cannot be an e_k , otherwise e_1 cannot scatter into the e_2 state. Thus,

$N p(e_1) N (1-p(e_k)) = \text{number of } e_1 \text{ particles} * \text{number of possible neighbours which are not } e_k$ ((2))

This then represents the total number of possible reactions of $e_1 \rightarrow e_k$.

We stress that the in ((1)), the total number of possible reactions expression is exact, even in the high N limit. It is the expression which would apply for a low N limit. This is markedly different from Stirling's approximation scenario $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ which is used in the a priori case of counting the number of states. Furthermore, Stirling's approximation is $n \ln(n) - n$ which means that one obtains different results if one uses $n \ln(n)$ or $n \ln(n) - n$ etc, while the expressions ((1)) have no such ambiguity or approximation.

As a result, we suggest that the notion of \ln appearing and a clear statistical picture are present in reaction balance. The question then becomes: How does one link this idea to the current idea of entropy?

Entropy

In Parts 1 and 2, we described how entropy arises from reaction balance. In particular, one postulates a function strictly of $p(e_i)$:

Sum over i $G(p(e_i))$ ((3)) such that:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } dG(p(e_i)) = A \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } e_i dp(e_i) + B \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

Given that one must find a link between e_i in ((4)) and a function of $p(e_i)$, we note that this is provided by reaction balance because ((1)) only holds for $e_1 + e_2 = e_k + e_l$. Thus, as argued in Part 2, $G(p(e_i))$ is of a statistical nature because ((1)) is of a clear statistical one. The question then becomes: What is the statistical nature of Sum over i $G(p(e_i))$?

We first note that reaction balance focuses on a single reaction, but at the same time considers all possible ways (global) in which this single reaction may occur. ((4)), on the other hand, is strictly a global view.

We suggest that if reaction balance consists of products of various kinds of probabilities with each factor being dependent only on one energy value, then taking \ln (logarithm) allows one to break the product into a sum and collect all same energy terms together such that these map to their respective e values as energy conservation must hold. The notion of:

$\ln(\text{probability } j)$ ((5)) exists where probability (j) may be unnormalized, but can only depend on one e value.

Given the math form, $\ln(\text{probability})$, one may mathematically identify this with Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((6))$$

The question, however, might be: Why should one take an exact statistical expression (number of possible successful interactions) found in reaction balance, and try to map it to an approximate factorial expression? Certainly, this can be done mathematically and given a factorial expression, one may try to map it to some kind of permutation scheme, we suggest that this may not be necessary. One already has a clear statistical picture in reaction balance ((1)), and we argue that there might not be a reason to seek a second statistical scenario, represented by entropy.

Nevertheless, mathematically one may use the form ((6)) because of ((4)). If one examines the FD case, one sees that:

$$N(p(e_1)) = \text{number of } e_1 \text{ particle and } N(1-p(e_k)) = \text{number of particles that are not } e_k \quad ((7))$$

One may always permute the various e_1 particles and the non- e_k particles and argue that this is a statistical measure of the system, albeit one described in the actual calculation in an approximate manner because of Stirling's approximation.

Given this view, one may consider $N!$ (or some other fixed N expression) divided by these permutations as representing a kind of unique set of permutations and then ((4)) has the mathematical form of:

Maximization of this approximate factorial expression subject to energy and probability constraints ((8))

We argue that this seems to be somewhat of a math approach due to the forcing of Stirling's approximation. One could just as well argue that:

$$p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ or } (1-p(e_i)) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((9))$$

are average expressions of $\ln(\text{probability}(j))$ where probability (j) may be unnormalized and not use Stirling's approximation at all. This bypasses the whole factorial picture, but is still linked with the statistical conservation of the number of possible successful interactions represented by reaction balance.

As a result, we suggest that the usual view of entropy may be somewhat of a math construct, albeit one that is certainly legitimate in light of Stirling's approximation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that reaction balance only applies to large N cases, because one examines a single reaction as being independent of others (which is strictly not the case). The main point we make (as in Part 1 and 2) is that one has a precise conserved statistical quantity, i.e. the number of successful reactions. This is not an approximate expression, even in the high N limit, as is Stirling's approximation. Thus, the statistical picture is exact. For the Fermi-Dirac case, one has $N p(e_1)$ = number of possible e_1 particles that might react and $N (1-p(e_k))$ = number of neighbours at the reaction point which are not e_k (otherwise e_1 cannot scatter into e_k). The product is exact. Reaction balance only applies together with conservation of energy

(elastic collisions) and so one may obtain the required MB, FD or BE distributions directly from reaction balance in a completely statistical well-defined manner.

If one decides to create an entropy function $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ where G is strictly a function of $p(e_i)$, and argue that $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$, then one introduces $\sum_i \ln(p(e_i))$ terms from reaction balance. These are mathematically of the form of Stirling's approximation and so one may "force" a factorial interpretation which then maps to a permutation scheme and one may argue that a factorial expression is being maximized subject to constraints. We suggest, however, that due to the approximate nature introduced by using Stirling's approximation, the exact statistical interpretation is in reaction balance. Furthermore, one may bypass the factorial scheme altogether by considering $\sum_i \ln(p(e_i))$ as being an average of $\ln(p(e_i))$.